

REAL-TIME DATA COMMUNICATION VIA BROADCASTING IN XPLANE-11

MUHAMMAD IBRAR

Pursuing Master's Degree Program in Electrical Engineering, Superior University, Pakistan.

Email: md.ibrar@superior.edu.pk

HAMID GULZAR

Technical Manager, Arab Technical Co Ltd., KSA. Email: Hamid.ali@arabtech-est.com

RIDA JAVAID

Lab Engineer, Department of Avionics Engineering, Superior University, Pakistan.

Email: rida.javaid@superior.edu.pk

TAHIR ZAIDI

Head, Department of Avionics Engineering, Superior University, Pakistan.

Email: tahir.zaidi@superior.edu.pk

USMAN AHMAD KHAN

Lab Engineer, Department of Avionics Engineering, Superior University, Pakistan.

Email: usman.ahmad@superior.edu.pk

MUHAMMAD IRFAN MUSHTAQ

Lecturer, Department of Avionics Engineering, Superior University, Pakistan.

Email: irfan.mushtaq@superior.edu.pk

TUBA AHSAN

Sales and Application Engineer, The Middle East Automation & Control Services, Pakistan.

Email: tubaahsan42@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper discusses the use of real-time data communication and reporting in the Xplane-11 flight simulation environment. The research focuses on the use of User Data Protocol for data transfer to provide seamless communication between the platform and the simulator. The main goal is to extend the flight chat time, improve data visualization on multiple screens, and enable data stream synchronization between Xplane-11 and MATLAB/Simulink. The paper outlines the integration process between these platforms, discusses the benefits of instant messaging, and compares Xplane-11 with other flight simulators such as Flight Gear. Through this research, we aim to create a robust simulation data transfer framework that increases the accuracy and precision of the virtual flight experience.

Index Terms: Xplane-11, Broadcasting, Virtual, Reality, Flight, Simulator, Protocol.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of simulation has gained importance in science and practical applications. A simulator is a software tool that reproduces real-world processes or situations in a virtual environment, allowing users to interact with and analyze the process without the risk or cost of real-world testing. There are many types of simulators used in various fields, such as flight simulators, medical simulators, air simulators, car simulators, electrical circuit simulators. These simulators provide excellent results by observing and performing complex tasks in a controlled virtual environment.

Flight simulators replicate the real-life behavior of aircraft systems, controls, and environments. Simulating the engine system can help users understand how external forces such as wind resistance, atmospheric pressure, and gravity affect flight [1]. The simulator also offers the opportunity to learn how different parts of the aircraft, such as the engine, landing gear, and flight controls, respond to these forces. Therefore, flight simulators can be used not only for pilot training, but also as research tools to explore aircraft systems, test new aircraft designs, and implement safety measures without risking the lives of real aircraft or people.

In this context, our research aims to develop a virtual flight simulator. A virtual simulator seeks to create a digital replication of real-world scenarios in which users can interact. The term "virtual" refers to the creation of an environment that closely resembles reality, yet it is computer-generated. This virtual environment allows users to engage with simulations as if they were interacting with the actual world. Virtual reality (VR) is one of the primary technologies that facilitate such experiences. With it, users may engage with a simulated world in real time, just like they would with the actual thing. Virtual reality (VR) includes a variety of immersive experiences, such as completely immersive, semi-immersive, non-immersive, and collaborative VR. Our research focuses on non-immersive virtual reality, which enables desktop or computer-based user interaction with the simulation.

Users that engage with a virtual world without being completely submerged in it are said to be using non-immersive virtual reality [2]. In contrast to completely immersive virtual reality (VR) systems, which necessitate the use of specialized gear like head-mounted displays (HMDs) or motion-tracking systems, non-immersive VR uses standard keyboards, mice, or joysticks to control and interact with the virtual environment shown on a regular screen. This type of VR is frequently employed in applications where the user still has to have a high degree of control and engagement but is not required to be physically present in the simulated world, such as in desktop flight simulators like X-Plane 11. Non-immersive VR is perfect for apps because it strikes a great mix between usability and accessibility like flight simulation, where the user can control the aircraft using a desktop interface without the need for full-body immersion.

In our research, we focus on non-immersive VR using X-Plane 11 to simulate flight in a desktop environment. Including detailed models of aircraft engines, weather, and control responses. X-Plane 11 allows for extensive customization, with users able to create a simulator to test a variety of scenarios, such as different weather conditions, aircraft malfunctions, and failures. This makes it a powerful tool for flight training, research, and testing.

One of the main features of X-Plane 11 is the broadcasting function, which allows users to send and receive information between the simulator and external devices or software. Broadcasting in X-Plane 11 can be done using the User Datagram Protocol (UDP), a communication protocol that allows data to be exchanged between the emulator and other systems in real time. This is particularly useful for researchers who want to integrate

Xplane-11 with external devices such as motion or control systems, as it allows the interaction to have an immediate effect on the simulator and physical equipment.

To extend the duration of the simulation, we will implement real-time data transfer, improving overall performance and displaying this data on multiscreen. By leveraging real-time communication, we aim to bridge the gap between the motion platform and simulator, ensuring a cohesive and realistic simulation experience. Typically, data is integrated in simulators by extracting it from the X plane and manually inputting it via USB. This ultimately limits the flight sessions to five to ten minutes.

Our research is focused on creating a virtual simulator using non-immersive VR technology. Since the simulator can exchange data with external devices in real-time through broadcasting in X-Plane 11, which is made possible by UDP communication, it is a powerful tool for research and experimentation in flight simulation. Using non-immersive VR in this context offers a workable and affordable solution for flight simulation, enabling users to interact with a highly realistic virtual environment without the need for specialized VR equipment. This research has the potential to advance the field of flight simulation and offer insightful information about the effects of sensory congruence on motion sickness in VR environments.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Xplane-11 is a well-known flight simulator with realistic effects. Xplane-11 was released in 2017 by Laminar Research. However, the Xplane-11 has a much longer development history, the initial release was Xplane-1 which was released in 1995. With continuous improvement, the version also changes. Now the Xplane-11 has a major update with the 64-bit architecture and VR support.

The X-plane simulator used the FITS (FAA-Industry Training Standards) approach [5], which is a partnership between the FAA (Federal Aviation Administration) industry and the academic community. The main goal of the FITS approach is to improve pilot training and reduce accidents. Therefore, the Xplane-11 provides us the realistic flight models and dynamics, enhances risk management, improves pilot proficiency and safety, and integration with FAA-approved training materials. Some of the popular aircraft that use the FITS complaint are Cessna 172SP, Piper PA-28-140, Beechcraft B58 Baron, Cirrus SR20.

As mentioned above, Xplane-11 follows the rules and guidelines given by the FAA. Xplane-11 supports the training scenarios follows FAA Part 61 Certification, it also aligns with the FAA Order 8900.1 (Flight standards Information Management System). Furthermore, the database used in Xplane-11 is also FAA approved such as navigational charts, airport diagrams, SIDS (Standard Instrument Departues), STARs (Standard Terminal Arrival Routes).

The X-plane's operational philosophy is based on analyzing an aircraft's geometric form to forecast its flight path. In essence, the airplane is disassembled into smaller parts, and the forces acting on each part are then computed using an engineering method known

as "blade element theory." The forces are then translated into acceleration according to the aircraft's mass and center of gravity. It then produces positions and velocities by acceleration.

Despite all other popular flight simulators in which each have their own unique strengths, the main reasons to choose Xplane-11 is given in the below table. In this table there is a complete comparison of the two flight simulators [6].

Table 1: Comparison of the Two Flight Simulators

Features	Xplane-11	Flight Gear
Source Code	It has a closed-source code	Open-Source code
Purchase	It requires purchase or subscription	It is free to download and easy to use.
Graphics	High quality graphics and performance	Variable graphics quality and performance
Licensing terms	Strict licensing terms	It is free to modify and distribute.
Community involvement	The development is led by Laminar Research	The Community drives development
FAA Certification	Xplane-11 is generally considered more accurate in simulating FAA rules and regulations. And certified as a BATD (Basic Aviation Training Device)	It incorporates the FAA- style rules and regulations, but not officially certified
Weather and Atmospheric Modelling	The weather engine simulates real world weather conditions	The weather engine is less advance than the Xplane-11
Flight Dynamics	It has the realistic flight dynamics, simulates the complex aerodynamics, weather and atmospheric conditions	It has a simplified flight dynamics and are less complex than Xplane-11
Supported Platforms	It supports multiple platforms like Windows, Mac OS, Linux [7].	It supports multiple platforms like Windows, Mac OS, Linux.

Therefore, by concluding the table, the major reasons for which we prioritize the Xplane-11 over all other flight simulators is in this paper we are focusing on flight dynamics and system simulation and preferring a well-polished, user friendly interface and high-quality graphics. As it covers the global scenery you can explore the world without restrictions, engage with simulated ATC, multiplayer, enhance training skills by the simulation modes. It is a better choice for professional pilots, flight training etc.

3. METHODOLOGY

The focus of our work is to enable real time communication between the motion platform and simulator, facilitating efficient data transfer and utilization, thereby eliminating potential discrepancies. In simulators, data is usually integrated, by X plane extracting it and then manually inputting it into the MATLAB via USB. It eventually limits the flight sessions to 5-10 minutes.

Figure 1: Manual Data Integration

To extend simulation duration, we will implement real-time data transfer, enhancing overall performance and display this data on multiscreen. By leveraging real-time communication, we aim to bridge the gap between the motion platform and simulator, ensuring a cohesive and realistic simulation experience. In result the manual data integration via USB is removed and a real time communication for the simulator is developed.

3.1 MATLAB/ Simulink Communication Protocol:

Xplane-11 transfer data using either UDP or C# to other applications or devices on the same network. We use UDP protocol to transfer data from Xplane-11 to MATLAB and vice versa. UDP is known as User Datagram Protocol. It is a way for computers to send messages to each other over the internet. The working of UDP can be defined as following in which data is first packaged into small packets, each packet has a destination address, packets are sent independently without the guarantee of arrival or order, no confirmation is sent back to the sender. In the broadcasting of the X-plane data and making of the motion platform, the SIMULINK helps in receiving the UDP packet from Xplane-11, processing of the received data and converted it into a form which is suitable for the simulation and post processing of data simulation and also the analysis and visualization of the output data. UDP is often used for real-time applications like video streaming, online gaming, or voice calls, where speed and efficiency are more important than ensuring every packet arrives. In the simulator we are using the UDP protocol for the main communication between the MATLAB and the flight simulator. The understanding of this concept is simply defined by the given block diagram [8].

Figure 2: Block Diagram of UDP communication

3.2 Casting:

The transmission of data over a network is called casting. There are different types of casting like broadcasting, unicasting, multicasting etc. Broadcasting means to send the information or data to everyone in a network at once, unicasting is sending the information to only one person and multicasting is sending the data to the selected group in a network [3]. The visual representation of the different types of casting is given below in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Types of casting

The main goal of our work is to do the broadcasting on Xplane-11. In simple terms, it refers to the transmission of data from one master computer to multiple recipients (slave computer) within the simulation environment. The master computer will control the aircraft and the multiple slave computers over the network will receive the data and the data will be shown on the multiple screens.

3.3 Integration:

The real-time communication will be carried out by the flight simulator Xplane-11 and the MATLAB. The mean of communication between the 2 software is UDP. The MATLAB/Simulink process the flight data from Xplane-11 for analysis [6]. The Xplane-11 simulates the data, and we can see the flight view. The Simulation concept is given as follows in the Fig. 4:

Figure 4: Simulation Diagram via UDP communication

3.4 Communication between MATLAB/ Simulink and Xplane-11:

The UDP (Use Datagram Protocol) is a means of communication between the two software MATLAB/ Simulink and X-plane-11. UDP helps in receiving and transfer of data. The communication protocol uses IP address and different ports. The IP addresses enable efficient, connectionless communication, enable multicasting, making it suitable for real-time applications. The ports are used for data communication or data transfer

between the different components. MATLAB/Simulink offers a UDP communication library, enabling data exchange through block programming. As a simple, efficient protocol, UDP facilitates near real-time communication with minimal latency. X-Plane adopts UDP as its standard protocol for sending and receiving data, seamlessly supported by MATLAB/Simulink. The primary benefit of UDP lies in its ability to transmit data with negligible delays, primarily limited by the Windows operating system's non-real-time nature.

3.5 Configuration of Xplane-11:

As we have discussed earlier that the communication is carried out by the UDP protocol. The setup for UDP communication setup consists of four access points, a unique port number for each access point and a single IP address [6]. The access points in the Xplane-11 refers to the specific location or the interfaces where the data can be shared between Xplane-11 and external system or applications [9]. The external application can be Arduino UNO or MATLAB/ Simulink and so on. But the communication between Xplane-11 and MATLAB/ Simulink has four access points, two for Xplane-11 and two for MATLAB/ Simulink. The two access points in Xplane-11 consists of a data output in which the aircraft condition, UDP rate and graph rate is described and a data input in which the data is received from the external source like Simulink. There is also a data input and data output access point in MATLAB/ Simulink. The data input shows the received data from the Xplane-11 and the data output shows the data that is to be send to the Xplane-11. The visual representation of the access points can be clarified by the following Fig. 5:

Figure 5: Access points in Xplane-11

For the selection of the output data, from Xplane-11 you have to the settings>data output>general data output. The data consists of all the parameters that shows the aircraft condition. The chosen data is then transmitted by the UDP communication. An aircraft's status is encoded in a 4-byte data set, split into nine distinct segments. For example, transmitting six navigation Fig.s requires 293 bytes of data, consisting of a 5-byte header followed by 288 bytes (8 x 9 x 4) of navigational data, The data output like frame rate, times, system pressure, weather, gear and brakes, angular movements, pitch, roll & headings, aircraft atmosphere, system pressure, propeller setting etc.

The network configuration is also shown in data output. In which the output data for the external source and the IP address and the port address is also given. In the below table you can see the IP address and port for Xplane-11.

Table 2: Simulator Ip Address Setting

Parameter	Values
Local IP Port	49004
Remote IP Address	127.0.0.1

3.6 Configuration in Simulink:

After configuring the communication port and the IP address, we use the MATLAB/ Simulink UDP blocks to send and receive data. It establishes a communication between MATLAB/ Simulink and the Xplane-11 [4]. The two types of blocks will be used in MATLAB/ Simulink which UDP sender and UDP receiver. The UDP sender sends the control commands or data from MATLAB/ Simulink to Xplane-11. The UDP receiver receives data from Xplane-11. The representation of the blocks is Simulink is given below fig. 6. The UDP receive block parameters is shown in Fig. 6. In this the local IP port, remote IP address, maximum buffer size and maximum length of the message is shown. The local IP port is the port number of UDP receiver block to receive the UDP packets [10]. The remote IP address is the IP address of the data sender machine. In this scenario we mention the IP address of the Xplane-11, which is the source of the UDP data. The maximum buffer size is the maximum amount of UDP that can be store in UDP receiver in its internal buffer before processing it. Once the data is received by the UDP receiver the byte unpacking is done. The byte unpacks block converts a vector of unit8, unit16 or unit32 data type to one or more signals of user-selectable data types. The UDP receive the package as the raw UDP packet. The byte unpacks block opens the package and extracts the contents, which is the original data. The UDP unpack data separate the header from the bytes before going to the decoder which eventually helps in identifying the packet, error detection of the packet and make the decoding easier.

Figure 6: UDP communication between MATLAB/Simulink and Xplane-11

The decoder block decodes the received UDP packets into the original data format, which includes the parameters like motor speed, different axis force, position of aircraft etc. After the decoding of data, it is sent to the UDP send block where data is sent directly over the network.

Table 3: Simulink Receiver Parameter Settings

Parameter	Values
Local IP Port	49004
Remote IP Address	127.0.0.1
Receive buffer size	8192
Maximum Length for Message	293
Data types for message	Unit8
Sample time	Inf

4. RESULTS

Our proposed research focus on the real-time communication system between X-Plane 11 and MATLAB/Simulink and also the display of the data on the multiple screens is done by broadcasting (in which the data is sent to all the computers at once) and it is shown can be easily understandable by the following Fig. 7:

Figure 7: Multiple screen display through broadcasting

Through the proposed research, the system the following results can be achieved like the simulation duration in flight simulator is extended because through manual integration of data via USB in the MATLAB, limit the flight sessions to 5-10 minutes. The data will be transmitted with less amount of delay in communication. Through broadcasting the same flight data is transfer from the master computer to multiple slave computer at once and the cohesive display on multiple screens. In result, the overall accuracy, functionality, performance and realistic simulation environment is created in the flight simulators.

5. CONCLUSION:

This study successfully integrated real-time data communication between X-Plane 11 and MATLAB/Simulink using UDP, overcoming limitations in flight simulation duration and enhancing data visualization. X-Plane 11's FAA compliance, realistic flight dynamics, and high-quality graphics made it the preferred simulator. Future research directions include integrating immersive VR in flight simulations, optimizing UDP for improved data accuracy and synchronization in real-time systems. This integration enables extended simulation times, multi-screen data visualization, and paves the way for advanced flight simulation applications.

Acknowledgment

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Allah Almighty for His guidance and blessings throughout this journey. Without His grace, this thesis would not have been possible. I would also like to thank my parents, especially my father, for their unwavering love, encouragement, and sacrifices. Their belief in me has been a constant source of motivation. Finally, I am grateful to all my friends and family members who have supported me throughout this process. Their encouragement and understanding have been invaluable.

References

- 1) Javaid, A., Rasool, S., & Maqsood, A. (2024). Analysis of Visual and Vestibular Information on Motion Sickness in Flight Simulation. *Aerospace*, 11(2), 139.
- 2) [https://retheme.com/types-of-virtual-reality/\(online_resources\)](https://retheme.com/types-of-virtual-reality/(online_resources))
- 3) <http://1.https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fcastr.com%2Fblog%2Funicast-vs-multicast-vs-broadcast%2F&psig=AOvVaw0slPxSDQaG3xYysiAPoQsh&ust=1727605324478000&source=image&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CBcQjhxqFwoTCKia9Ny15YgDFQAAAAAdAAAAABAc> (online resources)
- 4) Almazan-Arvizu, R. Y., Gutiérrez-Frías, O., Lozano-Hernández, Y., Rodríguez-Cortes, H., & Aguirre-Anaya, J. A. (2024). Validation in X-Plane of Control Schemes for Taking off and Landing Manoeuvres of Quadrotors. *Drones*, 8(8), 409.
- 5) Williams, B. (2011). *Scenario-Based Training with X-Plane and Microsoft Flight Simulator: Using PC-Based Flight Simulations Based on FAA-Industry Training Standards*. John Wiley & Sons.
- 6) Horri, N., & Pietraszko, M. (2022). A tutorial and review on flight control co-simulation using matlab/simulink and flight simulators. *Automation*, 3(3), 486-510.
- 7) Figueiredo, H. V., & Saotome, O. (2012, October). Simulation platform for quadcopter: Using matlab/simulink and x-plane. In *2012 Brazilian Robotics Symposium and Latin American Robotics Symposium* (pp. 51-55). IEEE.
- 8) Aschauer, G., Schirrer, A., & Kozek, M. (2015). Co-simulation of matlab and flightgear for identification and control of aircraft. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 48(1), 67-72.
- 9) Ribeiro, L. R., & Oliveira, N. M. F. (2010, October). UAV autopilot controllers test platform using Matlab/Simulink and X-Plane. In *2010 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE)* (pp. S2H-1). IEEE.
- 10) Kaviyarasu, A., & Kumar, K. S. (2014). Simulation of flapping-wing unmanned aerial vehicle using x-plane and matlab/simulink. *Defence Science Journal*, 64(4), 327.